

Embedding Non-Quantifiable Product Qualities in Products and Product Development

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Abstract

This paper describes and discusses some preliminary findings from research into how companies embed non-quantifiable product qualities into their products. Through 24 interviews within five case companies this exploratory research seeks to understand how non-quantifiable product qualities are treated and developed. The research has been conducted on the basis of grounded theory, following the experiences of companies involved in manufacture of mobile phones, hi-fi's and vehicles. The results show different levels of insight and understanding of important product qualities between the case companies, and address key elements in trying to ensure that a systematic and repeatable approach can be pursued. One of the preliminary conclusions is the lack of a developed and shared 'language' (verbal or non-verbal) among product developers, that could provide a richer communication, and thereby better understanding and embedding of the non-quantifiable product qualities.

Keywords: Intangible product qualities, socio-technical product development, case studies.

Introduction

Today many products position themselves in the market on the basis of qualities that are more than just purely technical. These qualities are often difficult to access for the designer due to their non-quantifiable character. This paper describes some preliminary findings from research into how companies embed these qualities that are hard to quantify. In this research they are referred to as non-quantifiable product qualities (NQPQ's). The aim of the research presented in this paper is to map the way industry think and deal with NQPQ's. By gaining an insight into practice in industry, the long-term aim is to add to our understanding and practice in order to ensure a consistent and repeatable embedding of NQPQ's throughout the product development processes. Finally this paper illustrates two key themes identified in the data and discusses their implications.

Increasing importance of NQPQ's

The situation in industry today is that manufacturers often have access to and can incorporate the same technological qualities into their products. Organisations are maturing their

technical capability and can rapidly copy Quantifiable Product Qualities (QPQ's). These qualities, being very similar and easy to copy, are therefore not valid product differentiators anymore. New ways of differentiating products are being used, preferably in ways that are difficult to copy. Industry is therefore increasingly concerned with product qualities such as usability, appearance (Macdonald, 1998), identity, semantic qualities (Möno, 1997 and Vihma, 1987), pleasure (Jordan, 2000, Flyte & Hauge-Nilsen, 2002) surprise and delight (Burns & Evans, 2000), comfort, ergonomics, context of use and environmental issues compared to cost, perceived quality (customer value) and product price. These qualities are often of subjective matter – they are likely to evoke emotional rather than rational response in the user and therefore they may be difficult to pinpoint, and thereby design and access. Another important aspect when understanding these qualities is that that the 'sum is bigger than the values of the individual parts'; NQPQ's are often difficult to identify on their own but have to be assessed as a whole (a gestalt), though they need to be designed individually.

These non-quantifiable product qualities are important to organisations and to design because they are the often product differentiators, and often have a strong effect when building brand. This research is not concerned with branding as a topic, but how companies organise to embed NQPQ's into the product; it therefore asks questions about design process, about how the designers work and interact, and not asking questions about the product itself.

Research strategy – Empirical data collection

In order to gain an insight into how companies understand, design and embed NQPQ's an exploratory and qualitative approach was pursued, to understand phenomena in their real context (Robson, 1993). This means studying real organisations, with all their complexity, and trying to find data meaningful to the study of NQPQ's. Mature organisations producing high volume products were targeted because it is felt that the NQPQ's will be of higher importance in the design process. This research is concerned with the NQPQ's in the product but excluding branding issues (specifically excluding the effect of brand names and logo's). The impact of branding is understood, and is of great significance, but is not the subject of this research. In this initial study, data were collected from five manufacturers; one Hi-Fi, one mobile phone and three vehicle manufacturers across Europe. This also allows the researcher to see if there are any industry similarities or differences. The next stage of the research will look closer at two development cases in two companies in order to gain a deeper and more

specific insight into how the NQPQ's are developed and embedded. This is done to identify factors or principles that can be further exploited into general guidelines.

Data was collected through interviews with various actors involved in the product development process. The semi-structured interview method was selected in order to 'get into peoples head's' and get them to describe their world, their perspective on NQPQ's, and their involvement when it comes to decisions, designing and evaluation of NQPQ's. Within each of the five organisations 4-6 people involved in product development were interviewed resulting in 25 interviews lasting 1-1½ hours each. Each of the interviews were taped and later transcribed. The interviewees included product and brand managers, industrial designers, product planners, engineers and area specialists (such as usability experts). It was important to interview people involved in the overall design as well as specific specialists in order to gain an insight into how people with different focus comprehend and disseminate NQPQ's.

Initial data analysis

The research method resulted in a very rich data set that illustrates various points, factors and phenomena that influence the embedding of NQPQ's (social settings, freedom of thought, ideas generation, customer insight etc.). The analysis of the interviews was done through a coding system where any interesting point were highlighted in the transcribed text, these were then printed out individually into many hundreds of pieces of paper. Similar statements were then grouped to begin the construction of themes. The 10 main themes that emerged during this first data analysis are listed below. In cases where individuals made statements that could be placed under more than one theme, they would be put under each theme.

List of identified themes:

1. Awareness of NQPQ's in general
2. The design process of embedding NQPQ's
3. Transformation of NQPQ's into QPQ's
4. Decision making process – who's responsibility are the NQPQ's?
5. Forum for discussing/debating NQPQ's within the organisation
6. Embedding NQPQ's in the specification

7. Customer insight - understanding who you design NQPQ's for and find out what the NQPQ's are to them
8. Culture/language of designers
9. Influence of pre-perception (previous) experiences
10. Cost - cost cutting and NQPQ cutting

In the next section two of the themes will be presented: Transformation of NQPQ's into QPQ's (theme 3) and Customer insight (theme 7). These have been selected as being of particular interest in this forum and as being particularly rich in their data.

Transformation of NQPQ's into QPQ's

Individual quotes were selected into this theme because they illustrated any attempt to transform product qualities of non-quantifiables (often emotional or intangible characteristics) into something that could be clearly defined in quantifiable terms or numerical measures. There appear to be two distinct notions of the transformation of NQPQ into quantifiable measures. One is the quantification of the 'physical' quality itself - for example breaking 'driveability' or 'sound' down to specific and measurable characteristics. The other is to quantify the response to a product quality - such as using customer or expert ratings to quantify the 'success' of a specific or complex product quality (asking customers to rate the overall feeling of pleasure when using the product).

The following section illustrates some of the data that was filtered into this theme:

The next two statements illustrate that even complex product qualities, like the steering feel of a car or product noise/sound, may be broken down to core physical elements and be quantified:

... 'we try as much as possible to break the subjective down to supporting objective items. So even noise you could say from a customer point of view is subjective, but we can break it down to objective measurements'.

... 'Well I guess it has to become...if you want an engineer to design something, if you are well aware, you have got to give them something to design too. So it does have to be quantified. And we have...on things that, you know, perhaps a layman might think is something like steering is not quantifiable. The engineers will know how much friction there

should be in the system, what the torque should be in the rates of response and the effect, under which they will have all of that quantified. They have a set of parameters that they design too, and they also... you might when you talk to other people they might talk about the (brand name's) DNA which is our steering DNA. And that will be the design parameters within which they will develop the various steering characteristics, so it has a (brand name) feel to it'.

This statement illustrates the belief in a commutable link between quantifiable parameters and how they add up to a certain 'feel' - the non-quantifiable quality, that the product should deliver a certain brand-specific feel to the users. The statement also illustrates the belief that repeatable use of these specific quantifiable parameters will send out a signal of consistency in product characteristics and enforce the notion of a brand DNA.

The next statement illustrates the belief that certain product characteristics drive the customer's recognition of what makes a particular type of product. E.g sports cars are sports cars because of these (wide tires, low body profile, aerodynamic shape, agile steering dynamic etc.), but they also have other characteristics. Even the 'sports carness' of a sports car is turned into a measure by making direct benchmark comparisons to existing sports cars! ...*'There is very much a platform quantifiable statistic which is around what constitutes a small car, what constitutes a classical affirmation of a B car, C car, D car, luxury segment, MPV, SUV and proportions related to product design'.*

...*'And whilst design is measured in the main by the designer's eye, those quantifiable statistics are either supporting or driving, depending on the priorities being attached to a product design'.*

By referring to existing established product qualities, the non-quantifiable qualities are referenced back to 'benchmark-measures' that have evolved from past product executions.

Some examples of how the case companies attempted to get 'reliable' numerical scores for these non-quantifiable attributes through the use of index systems:

...*'We have our own index internally. We have perceived quality - the global standard that we apply where we judge things. And we have basically skilled people around the globe and we frequently re-visit our product - and we survey the market just to make sure that we continually correlate to public opinion'.*

...*'I think we measure a lot. The only difference is that in terms of measurements it is this internal measurement system, which the sceptics outside can say 'but that is only your*

opinion'. Okay it might be opinion that is correlated between the members of the xx team or it might even be correlated to market opinion in some respect. But it is still only subjective...'

These statements illustrate that non-quantifiable product quality is often measured through an internal measurement system - often an index system. Index systems can be said to create a point of reference for evaluating product quality. The quote also illustrates that the non-quantifiables may be assessed by experts, so that they can become pseudo-quantified. Also that surveys are used to try to find out the general perception in the market. It seems to be important to have lots of different types of people to assess the product qualities, although the data shows that 'skilled' people have a high influence on the assessment.

Asked about how they handle design features or aspects of the product that they can not necessarily measure:

... 'Well we do measure them. Whether or not it is a robust measurement system is another argument'.

... 'Yah, but also....I will tell a target figure. We have a 1-10 digit scale at (company name), so I would put a target figure for each complete car. Like 8.0 could be one target figure but then I have divided it down...into exterior quality, interior quality, so I could say that the instrument panel must reach 8.5 or 8.6... ordinary customers or internal customers, they would come to a clinic - they will look at the car and they will follow the questions....You would ask the questions 3 at a time and you click in a box from 1-10 what you think about the different items...'

The importance of turning the NQPQ's into QPQ's is evident in the two following quotes.

The first quote refers to a design review process:

... 'Unfortunately the business climate means if it does not have a number or a positive number to support the cost, which is a negative, then it does not ...it is very difficult for people to keep it there and not consider deletion'.

It appears to be challenging to defend a non-quantifiable attribute against challenge from the well-quantified cost.

... 'And I can guarantee when I go and make this presentation to the people who hold the purse strings for the new project, they will say "We can't afford this, go back and quantify how much value this has to the market. How many cars will we sell more... And that is where the problem starts, because it is almost impossible'.

It is evident in all the cases that companies are transforming qualities that in their nature are non-quantifiable into quantifiable measures. This is often done by breaking a particular quality (like for instance 'usability' or 'driveability') down to several sub-qualities that are targeted and assessed through the use of quantifiables i.e. numbers. The notion of non-quantifiable as being something that can be turned into objective measures does not apply in all cases. In some cases the qualities are transformed from being intangible into being more tangible through less objective methods, where individual perception is a key factor (such as benchmarking). Benchmarking is where competitor products or even non-familiar product are compared in order to position a current product under development or already launched products.

The data show similarity between the case companies. Specific methods might differ, but all are trying to break down the NQPQ's into more quantifiable or tangible qualities. Where physical measures can not be used, organisations seek other quantifiable methods and the use of benchmarking is common. The car manufacturers seem to have a stronger tradition for turning NQPQ's into numeric measures. The reason behind this might be that a lot of the technical and physical qualities in a vehicle have not changed over many years, whereas the mobile phone industry keeps developing the product fundamentals by adding new technologies and thereby new features.

There are various levels of understanding on how to turn non-quantifiables into quantifiables. On the very basic level, it seems important to measure things in figures because the number system creates a base that we can not argue about and it gives the assessment a point of reference that everyone in the design process will understand.

The Quality-Quantity Deployment model, Figure 1, illustrates the spectrum of methods observed by the author for embedding NQPQ's – to the left the intangibles are kept in a non-quantifiable language throughout the product development process, whereas moving towards the right they are turned into harder and harder quantifiable (QPQ) measures. From the case studies it is clear that the ambition of many companies is to move to the right – towards absolute measures.

The Quality-Quantity Deployment model illustrates various intangible qualities remaining intangible through product development e.g. qualities that remain difficult to define and

measure. These qualities can be observed as being handled in the design process on the basis of instinct or ‘gut’ feelings.

Since these intangibles are so difficult to describe on their own they are often easier to describe when given a reference point e.g. a benchmark. By using physical benchmarks intangible qualities (and the emotional response they evoke) can be made ‘visible’ and communicated. Getting harder still, the need for measuring has led to the development of index systems, where qualities are quantified/marked according to a numeric system.

Finally some NQPQ’s are assessed purely on the basis of quantifiables (numeric) measures; these qualities are themselves based on physical properties and represent the extreme of transforming an NQPQ into QPQ’s (even though they may not fully represent the NQPQ).

Figure 1, Quality-Quantity Deployment model

Customer insight - Understanding who you design NQPQ’s for and find out what the NQPQ’s are to them

The criterion for filtering quotes into this theme was comments that would add understanding or help answer to: ‘how a company finds out about non-quantifiable (emotional, etc) responses to a product?’

Embedding NQPQ’s like for instance usability, product appeal, fun, pleasure and delight have obvious links to the users’ experience of the product. Customer insight is seen as being very important to the successful embedding of NQPQ’s, so companies often seek customer

feed-back to improve the chances of product success. But there are also aspects where the user can not easily help the manufacturers because the user can only take the perspective of today and cannot predict even their own reactions when a product is launched in the future. This section illustrates the use of customers to inform and assess the embedding of NQPQ's in the development process. It also includes comments about what the interviewees wish to know from potential customers.

When asked about how much of the embedding of product qualities should be based on customer insight two interviewees from different companies answered:

... 'We actually work to a rule of 80/20. 80% is us - 80% is design driven directions. 20% is looking at customer's responses, insight and commentary'.

... 'so they have done a lot of research on this because it is a new (market) area as well for (company name). So they have actually gone out to try and find where the market is ...and...let's say Africa or South America and I think they (marketing dept.) spend 3-4 month doing this...and then they came back and presented us...showed us what they found, which I thought was very good....'

Although the statement is given in relation to customer insight, it seems like the research is conducted at a separate, more market oriented, level. The market insight can ensure that overall understanding of desired product qualities related to specific culture is achieved. This broad insight can help to illuminate potential 'danger' areas when embedding NQPQ's, but it is unlikely to influence the product design specifically since the product is market globally:

... 'So it is the same product that goes to every single market, so they basically have to drag a bit of each area into this (product)'.

When asked: 'When do you use customer insight' this interviewee answered;

... 'We will use them (past or potential customers) very often, but we won't limit ourselves to what they have said is good. We always have to try to build on top of that'.

... 'But ultimately the problem that you've got, even if you get very precise feedback from our customers you've got to recognise their limitations, because they'll say what is nice to them. And our job is to think well that is nice today but in three years time you might not like it anymore and they've moved on'.

The interviewee is aware of the time factor when asking customers opinion today knowing that a product will be launched in 1-5 years.

Several of the interviewees expressed the view that a deeper understanding of customer values, lives and emotions were important to them when designing products:

... 'And understanding what their attitudes/values are and looking at their transportation needs and wants. And then, what we did was to develop several vehicle concepts so, full vehicle concepts to suit their needs. And more importantly, attitudes and emotional aspirations, so obviously that is a lot of style'

... 'We had a clinic like that, with qualitative research, where we actually had people going into the homes of our customers and talking about the product for several hours and also the environment they are living in and so on'.

... 'Well we do a huge amount of customer research and if we are developing a new vehicle, that will go through... well we go through various phases. Very early on in the program or even before the program, we do what we call a consumer immersion. So the engineers and the marketing brand people and the program teams and so on will basically find out as much as they can about the customer'.

All of the participating companies had ways of getting customer insight. Car manufacturers often clinic designs or aspects of the design early on in the concept stages using 'experts', potential and existing customer. Whereas the mobile phone industry seemed only to use internal people, that would know about market preferences, special use or perceptions throughout the development phases. The car manufacturers have a concise customer insight at market level, but some of them have also more personal, qualitative customer insight in order to understand certain segments.

Conclusion - Language and common understanding

The two themes and many quotes illustrate the diversity of different ways that companies are handling NQPQ's. Although there seems to be no well defined and tested design process for embedding NQPQ's, it is evident from the data that the embedding of NQPQ's goes through different phases. Firstly of being articulated – NQPQ's are talked about amongst the design team, often by describing their end-result (such as an emotion the qualities should evoke in the end user). By referring to 'feelings' that the product should evoke - 'it should feel like a user-friendly interface', the concept of 'user-friendliness' is simplified to the user emotion. These are then made sensible/visible through their embodiment (for example instant feedback to the user when interacting with the interface). Very often companies then try to

quantify the product qualities – the NQPQ’s are turned into QPQ’s, which allows a more standardised design and testing procedure to work effectively. The process is illustrated in the ‘NQPQ language’-model below.

Figure 2, NQPQ’s language model.

Although the transformation of NQPQ’s into QPQ’s is observed to be a strong force in product development, with companies wanting to increase quantification if possible. There also seems to be recognition of the importance of embedding the ‘hard to define qualities’ and growing acknowledgement that they are in an intangible format. Companies are becoming more comfortable with a design process that spans both the QPQ lower route **and** the descriptive route that allows for non-quantifiable qualities. One such mechanism is observed in the use of benchmarking as adding to communication and comprehension of NQPQ’s as one interviewee puts it:

‘I mean it is difficult because you can not - you can not see it immediately so you need to hear it, and try it out and discuss it: ‘okay, so what is it exactly you mean’ so when you have a benchmark and something you can relate to - both of you - it becomes much easier. It is about, as you said, to get a common language and a common understanding of where it is we want to go’.

This quote illustrates a common solution to making the NQPQ’s ‘visible’ or comprehensible, so that a group of people will reach a common understanding, through building a language that allows them to share tacit understanding (knowledge) or create a ‘common cognitive ground’ as described by Nonaka & Takeuchi (1995).

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